

Revising The Base Logic of Division

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Abstract

Conventional division at this time, in its inverse multiplication logic, is not seemingly compatible with the alternative multiplication established by Aku L. T. Jutila in *One Times One Equals Two*. Therefore, this paper shall establish the conventional multiplication system as compatible with the alternative multiplication system through altering away the inverse multiplication logic, while retaining the practical application of the conventional division, and additionally presenting division by zero, though not necessary to the alternative division itself.

I. Introduction

Division as elementary arithmetic at this time, is managed as inverse multiplication, as the accepted convention. However, the inverse multiplication convention is not compatible with the alternative multiplication proposed in *One Times One Equals Two*¹ by Aku L. T. Jutila. Therefore, this note exists to form an alternative division compatible with the alternative multiplication.

II. Proposal

Taking the used system's current notation, $a \times b = a \times b + a$, we can see that inverse multiplication fails immediately, as shown by the following example:

$$20 \div 5 = 4$$

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$$4 \times 5 = 24$$

$$5 \times 4 = 25$$

¹ Aku L. T. Jutila, *One Times One Equals Two*, Zenodo (2026), <https://zenodo.org/records/20157082>.

If inverse multiplication cannot serve as the logic for division, then what logic will make it compatible with the alternative multiplication, at least on an elementary arithmetic level, as both are primarily demonstrated on such level at this time?

The new logic shall be the exact same way division works in conventional division, except without requiring inverse multiplication. It can also be then given that division by zero may return the original number, as there is no requirement for inverse multiplicativity, leaving division by zero to be possible to be justified as the dividend being divided to no one, leaving it the same, though not necessary to do so.

$$3 \div 3 = 1$$

$$2 \div 2 = 1$$

$$1 \div 1 = 1$$

$$235 \div 0 = 235$$

$$54 \div 32 = 1.6875$$

$$23 \div 75 = 0.3066666667$$

While not necessarily elegant, the applied results of conventional division are still useable with the alternative multiplication used, dropping inverse multiplication as a base logic, without altering the rest of it, except possibly division by zero, though it is not necessary to reform it. In essence, now division is independent from being explained by multiplication, by removing its original base logic, but retaining its results, except possibly for division by zero, allowing for the two operations to co-exist, unless shown otherwise. It may not explain why three divided by three is one, but the result is retained regardless.

As the final conclusion is, Jutila's alternative multiplication only seems to conflict with conventional division, if division is required to be able to be inversely multiplied.